

Enhancing Higher education through Skill development

Prof. Dr .Daksha Dave

Professor, Smt. M.M.P.Shah Women's College of Arts and Commerce Matunga-19

Corresponding author- **Prof. Dr .Daksha Dave**

Email: daks.dave1965@gmail.com

Abstract

A basic criterion for being employable is skill. Unfortunately, higher education has been greatly extended in India, yet young people with low skill levels are still experiencing unemployment. According to the India Skill Report (2020), which provides an early look at the talent landscape in the country, 47% of the population is currently employable, which is impacted by changes in the required skills and the kind of work. India has a problem with educated unemployment as a result of students' poor talent even after graduation. In order to allay these worries, the Indian government has launched a number of initiatives aimed at helping young people develop useful skills. The government has also created a revolutionary "New Education Policy 2020" to offer a more extensive skill upgrading plan and employable skills. Many challenges are in achieving this target. Here researcher is focusing on "Skill development in Higher Education: Issues and Challenges" Researcher found that many challenges have been facing in implementation of skill development programme.

Key Words: Higher Education, Skill development, New Education Policy, Employability Gap

Introduction:

"Vidya sarvatra poojite" which means knowledge is worshipped everywhere. This proverb is indicating that knowledgeable person is getting respect across the geographical boundary. Fortunately India has diversified knowledgeable people who has given name and fame to India such as Sundar Pitchai, Satyam Nandela, Dr. Subramanian, Indranaiyee Noor, Nobel laureate Abhijit Benrjee etc. Higher education system makes substantial contributions to its economic, social, and political development. India has world 3rd largest higher education system. The Moto of the higher education is to develop the learners all round personality. According to Yorke, (2006) However, the present era demands that developing the requisite employability potential also is included as one of the important objectives of higher education. It is also noteworthy that one of the key reasons why many students investing in university education is to improve their employment prospects. This Implies that while achievement of good academic qualifications is highly valued, it no longer appears sufficient to secure employment. India Skill Report (2020) gives a sneak peek at the talent landscape in the nation, noting that 47% of the population is currently employable, which is impacted by shifts in the need for skills and the nature of work. Due to students' weak talent even after graduation, there is an issue with educated unemployment in India. To address these concerns, the Indian government has established a number of programs for young people to improve their employable skills. To provide a larger skill upgrading programme and employability skills, the government has also designed a ground-breaking "New Education Policy 2020." India's higher education sector is expanding at an unparalleled rate, as seen by the rise in enrollments, the number of institutions, and the amount of public

support. The task of giving an increasing number of students equal access to high-quality higher education, addressing sectoral and social inequalities, revitalizing institutions, surpassing global excellence benchmarks, and extending knowledge frontiers is becoming more and more challenging (Saini, 2015). The Global Talent Competitiveness Index 2019 claims that because of the changing global environment, countries had to alter their higher education policies. As a critical engine of long-term growth, higher education in the US and China has already experienced major changes. India has made important advancements in higher education as well. Our higher education system will become more globally competitive as a result of the new education policy's emphasis on more vocational and multidisciplinary education.

Literature Review:

1)Dr. S.C. Patil and Prof. Amaresh B. Charantimath conducted a study in 2021 titled "Employability through Skill Development Programmes - an Overview of Significance of Employability Skills" with the goals of identifying the significance of employability skills and identifying the discrepancy between expected skills and skills inculcated. The study's conclusions indicate that effective stakeholder involvement, including that of candidates, governments, educational institutions, and training partners, can raise the employability rate. The infrastructure facilities must be upgraded, and the curriculum must be revised to include a connection between industry and institution. By working together, the public and private sectors can guarantee that skill development initiatives are adequately financed, managed, and assessed.

2)Anita Swain and Sunita Swain (2020) conducted a study on "Skill Development in India: Challenges & Opportunities" with the intention of highlighting

the various difficulties Indian youth face as well as various government programmes like Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojna, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana, etc. and analysing the data obtained from the National Skill Development Corporation. According to the report, India has a "demographic dividend," but it must take advantage of it to gain from it. By guaranteeing a highly skilled workforce, it can strengthen the economy and aid the "Make in India" initiative. In order to increase job creation in the nation, the Skill India efforts must concentrate on fostering stronger entrepreneurial skills among the workforce.

3) Dr. Rajni Arora and Manoj Chhadwani (2019)

,According to their A study on "Analyzing the Impact of Skill India as a Tool for Reshaping Indian Economy", the Skill India Mission must be properly implemented in order to increase momentum. The government has set an ambitious goal of skilling 400 million people by 2022, however it is clear that the pace is far slower and the rate of training/skilling to job/placement transfer is not performing up to expectations. Only 1.97 million of the 2.4 million people who were supposed to be trained in the first phase of the project did so. In India, there is a severe lack of skilled labourers with only 2.3% has formal skill training, compared to South Korea's 96%, Japan's 80%, Germany's 75%, the United Kingdom's 68%, and the United States of America's (52%). This underlines the need for quick attention to improving people's skills and efficient execution of the full skill India Mission process.

4) A. Krishnamoorthy and H. Srimathi (2019),

did a study titled "Skill Development - The Future of India" with the intention of reviewing the current norms in the various skill sets that are accessible and outlining potential future directions. According to the study's findings, India may have the greatest youthful workforce over the next two decades, but this won't be enough on its own. This achievement cannot be made possible by arbitrary rule of law. The need for a skilled workforce must be carefully considered, and appropriate measures must be implemented to transmit vocational and associated skills in accordance with industrial demands. With a blended approach that incorporates all the best practices in skill development on need-based analysis, introspections, periodic revisions, and coherent contribution, Indians can have a strong hold in the global workforce and also sustain growth and development.

Objectives:

1. To discuss an overview of Indian Higher education
2. To discussed the need of skill based higher education
3. To explain the challenges in implementation of skill in higher education

4. To suggest some remedies for skill based education

Research Methodology:

The entire study is based on secondary data .However researcher has tried to collect the data through authentic sources, especially Government reports and international reports and research reports.

An Overview of Indian Higher Education:

According to AISHE report 2021, there are 1043 Universities at all India level, 42343 Colleges and 11779 Stand Alone Institutions. 307 Universities are having affiliating Colleges. 396 Universities are privately managed, 420 Universities are located in rural area.17 Universities are exclusively for women, 3 in Rajasthan, 2 in Karnataka and Tamil Nadu & 1 each in Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Uttarakhand and West Bengal. In addition to 1 Central Open University, 14 State Open Universities and 1 State Private Open University, there are 110 Dual mode Universities, which offer education through distance mode also and the maximum 13 of them are located in Tamil Nadu. There are 522 General, 177 Technical, 63 Agriculture & Allied, 66 Medical, 23 Law, 12 Sanskrit and 11 Language Universities and rest 145 Universities are of other Categories. The top 8 States in terms of highest number of colleges in India are Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat. From 3.85 crore in 2019–20, the total number of students enrolled in higher education has climbed to about 4.14 crore in 2020–21. The number of students enrolled has increased by almost 72 lakh (21%) from 2014–15. The number of female students has increased from 1.88 million in 2019–20 to 2.01 Female enrollments as a share of total enrollment climbed from 45% in 2014–15 to roughly 49% in 2020–21. The GER of ST students shows a significant increase of 1.9 points between 2020–21 and 2019–20.

Why India Need Skill-Based Higher education?

1) **To Fill the Employability Gap:** A new research from TeamLease Degree Apprenticeship claims that the nation is suffering with substantial skill gaps and that just a small portion of the workforce is officially skilled. Approximately 49% of the country's youth (aged 22 to 25) are employable, which indicates that one in two Indian youth are unemployed. A skill deficit in the industry was cited by about 75% of the organizations polled.

The National Employability Report for Engineering, which claims that roughly 80% of Indian engineers lack the abilities necessary to meet employers' standards, also highlights the talent gap. According to a recent NASSCOM report, the demand-supply gap will widen by 3.5 times by 2023

By 2023, it is anticipated that more than two million positions in block chain, cyber security, and AI would go vacant. The issue has also been exacerbated by digitalization, the adoption of automation, and AI across industries, as the available experts cannot advance into these sought-after professions because they lack the technical expertise for these new and developing job profiles. According to the Team Lease survey, businesses are in increasing need of a qualified staff as their prospects for growth and competitiveness are in jeopardy.

2) To Take the Advantage of Demographic Dividend; through various interventions, such as skill-based education combining work-integrated and experiential learning, as well as skill training and development, India's enormous population may be transformed into a benefit of alive demographic dividend and trained society. The country may transition from a labor-intensive to a skill-intensive economy and achieve inclusive development by investing in skill-based education, learning, and training. The most important factors for economic growth, according to Nilsson (2010), are skill-based education, learning, and skill training. Skill-based education is crucial for students to acquire job-related competencies and transform from job seekers to job producers.

3) To Achieve the Goal of Skill India Mission: The "Education Plan," sometimes referred to as the Eleventh Five-Year Plan, places a major emphasis on skill development and academic programmes for higher education in this regard (Cabral & Dhar, 2019). Essentially, the goal of the plan was to take into account the National Skill Development Objective, and the Ministry of Labour and Employment has published the "National Policy on Skill Development" to carry out that goal. Additionally, UGC has added vocational courses in every stream.

Challenges in Skill –Based Education:

The Government of India has initiated several key initiatives to integrate skill-based education in Higher education sector. But, still there are several challenges that need to pay immediate attention which are described in below.

1. Lack of Coordination among the institution and Industry: There is still lacking the coordination among the prominent stakeholders of the academia-industry network that is the Educator, Educatee and the Employer.
2. Lack of adequate and timely quality training for the trainers and the teaching staff.
3. There is still the presence of perception bias about skill-based and vocational education in India.
4. Lack of infrastructure and modern equipment is the challenge. There is a lack of existence of

adequate and quality skill labs/laboratories, machinery, tools and equipment's, skill apt curriculum in association with industry experts and other support systems.

5. The presence of skill universities/institutions are disproportionate in comparison to the population size of Indian diaspora.

Key Recommendations:

Following are some of the recommendations that have been suggested to the institutions, Policymakers, regulators and allied stakeholders to resolve such challenges in the context of India.

1. Comprehensive collaboration across government, business, and academia. To participate, plan, and implement the strategies within the current educational system and cooperate, there needs to be deliberate triangular collaboration amongst these stakeholders.
2. Enhancing industry-institute engagement through work-integrated learning activities, experiential learning, internships, and industrial mentorship programmes, which will strengthen the connection between industry and academia.
3. In order to increase the capacity for skill development, it is imperative to place a strong emphasis on creative, complementary, and collaborative models like the Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) model, which allows for increased participation from the public and private sectors overall.
4. Educational institutions must make sure that every member of the teaching staff has the necessary credentials and work experience, that they received training before beginning their careers as teachers, and that they continue to do so. The establishment of teaching training institutions in India should be significantly increased in this regard.
5. Greater efforts should be made to strengthen the adaptability of multidisciplinary education and training systems, and study and work should be integrated into the mainstream curriculum to foster the development of transferable abilities in students, which can be useful.
6. The government should to play a major role in enhancing the visibility of skill and vocational education. Additionally, by raising public awareness and consciousness, society's perspective and traditional viewpoint on skills and vocational education are being changed.
7. Significant improvement of the system of skill-based education and training in higher education, as well as infrastructure and architecture supporting training.

8. Increasing the integration and reach of "dual system"-based skill education and training in India's higher education system.

Conclusion

The researcher emphasized the need of supporting skill-based education for the transformation of young graduates into prepared workers in the employment market in order to provide insight into the skill-based higher education. Through skill-based education, one can develop employability skills such as technical, problem-solving, creative, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork abilities. Additionally, the researcher listed the difficulties still faced by India's talent development system and made ideas that would be useful in overcoming those difficulties. In conclusion, higher education institutions, which include universities and learning institutes, must prioritize and align themselves more with skill-based education in order to meet the demands of the global workforce.

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